

RŮMĚNÍK

103

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I present to you the second issue of Ruměnik – this time a shorter pictorial focused on Czech native gold. In the future, I would like to prepare a more extensive book on this subject and publish the photographs also on mindat.com. That is why this issue serves rather as a shorter preview.

Two things may surprise you while reading:

One of the specimens no longer exists – it was destroyed during a peculiar experiment. And the specimen labelled as “from Křepice” may not in fact come from Křepice at all. I obtained it already under this name, which has its own charm – it refers back to the famous history of the 1920s.

I wish you a pleasant viewing!

Miloš Večeřa

Jílové u Prahy

Zlaté Hory

Křepice - Stožice

Stupná - Vidochov

Krásná Hora nad Vltavou

Otava - river

Brtnička - creek

Bojovský - creek

Brslenka - river

Next issue?
Photoluminescence

RUMĚNÍK¹⁰³

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